

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**EFFICACY OF CLOZAPINE IN THE TREATMENT OF
SCHIZOPHRENIC PATIENTS:
A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW**

Asmaa Mesfer Alshehri ¹, Lamis Hisham Bosi ², Afnan Muslah Alshahrany ¹
Yahya Mohammed Alreemi ³, Ahmad Mahmmod Balosh ³, Eman Abdulla Meshawi ¹,
Eman Ayed Almhgany ¹, Khadejah Mohammad Alshahrany ¹

¹Collage of Medicine, King Khalid University, Abha

² Collages of Medicine, Um-Alqura University, Makkah

³ Psychiatric Department, King Abdulaziz University, Makkah, Saudi Arabia

Abstract:

Introduction: Efficacy of clozapine was found superior to other conventional antipsychotic medications in treatment of schizophrenic patients, however many patients were found resistant to clozapine. In this review we aimed to review the evidence that supports use of clozapine as a monotherapy for treatment of schizophrenic patients.

Methods: A web-based search was implemented in MEDLINE database to find clinical trials conducted in human and written in English language. Excluded studies were trials assessed the effect of clozapine on levels of laboratory parameters, trials used augmentation pharmacological strategies, trials used adjunctive therapy, trials assessed only discontinuation rate, or dose titration. Further exclusion was made based on full text reading and many studies were excluded.

Results: The search resulted in 238 articles, of which only 26 articles found related to the review topic in the primary screening step. In the secondary screening, after full text retrieval, 10 studies were excluded. The included studies in this review were 16 clinical trials which fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The efficacy of clozapine in treatment of schizophrenic patients was higher than any comparison medication in the majority of the included studies.

Conclusion: This review supported the evidence of using clozapine in treatment-resistance patients either in adults or children schizophrenic patients, particularly when small doses were used.

Keywords: Efficacy, Tolerability, Clozapine, Antipsychotic, Schizophrenia

Corresponding author:**Asmaa Mesfer Alshehri**

Collage of Medicine,
King Khalid University,
Abha

QR code

Please cite this article in press Asmaa Mesfer Alshehri et al., *Efficacy of clozapine in the treatment of schizophrenic patients: A systematic review.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(01).

INTRODUCTION:

Schizophrenia is a condition of heterogeneous manifestations differs from patient to patient with various symptoms and outcomes [1]. It begins usually before 25 years old and affects about 1% of the entire population with equal gender distribution, however younger males and older females are affected more than older males and younger females, respectively. Schizophrenia characterized by different subsyndromes of delusions, hallucination and bizarre behavior [2].

There is no a definite treatment of schizophrenia and it mainly depends on a combination of pharmacological and psychological approaches. Medications used in treatment of schizophrenia are usually associated with adverse effects such as weight gain and xerostomia [3]. Despite antipsychotic medications are effective against most schizophrenic patients, about a fifth of patients do not respond to the treatment. These medication-resistant patients are a public health challenge characterized by severe symptoms and expanded duration of hospital care. Several second-generation medications have been developed and tested in order to improve response and reduce discontinuation [4]. Efficacy of clozapine was found superior to other conventional antipsychotic medications in treatment of schizophrenic patients, however many patients were found resistant to clozapine [5]. Different strategies have been used to manage these extra-resistant patients included augmentation pharmacotherapy, transcranial magnetic activation, and electrical convulsive treatment [6,7]. In this review we aimed to review the evidence that supports use of clozapine as a monotherapy for treatment of schizophrenic patients.

METHODS:

A web-based search was implemented 21/11/2018 through MEDLINE database using keywords [clozapine AND schizophren* And (effectiveness OR efficacy)] to identify relevant studied. The resultant studies were filtered according to the

inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria were clinical trials conducted in human and written in English language. Excluded studies were trials assessed the effect of clozapine on levels of laboratory parameters such as plasma cortisol, orexin, and insulin. Additionally, trials used augmentation pharmacological strategies and trials used adjunctive therapy to clozapine such as reboxetine, ziprasidone aripiprazole, haloperidol duloxetine lithium, sulpiride or minocycline were excluded. Trials assessed only discontinuation rate or dose titration were also excluded. Furthermore, studies aimed to evaluate cost effectiveness, to assess the tolerability or treatment of clozapine side effects such as hypersalivation were excluded. At the next step, the full texts were retrieved for the eligible studies. Further exclusion was made based on full text reading and many studies were excluded (Figure 1). The data were extracted from the included studies into the tables summarized the characteristics of the included studies, properties of schizophrenic patients, regime of medications including comparison medication if present, and the efficacy of the clozapine.

Foot note: PANSS = Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale,

Note: NDMC = N-desmethylclozapine; CGI = Clinical Global Impressions; CGAS = Children's Global Assessment Scale; BPRS = Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale; SAPS = Scale for the Assessment of Positive Symptoms; SANS = Scale for the Assessment of Negative Symptoms.

Figure (1): Flow diagram of the included studies in the systematic review

RESULTS:

The search resulted in 238 articles, of which only 26 articles found related to the review topic in the primary screening step. In the secondary screening, after full text retrieval, 10 studies were excluded due to reasons demonstrated in figure 1. The included studies in this review were 16 clinical trials which fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The sample size recruited in the included studies ranged from 25 schizophrenic children in Shaw *et al.* [8] to 325 participants in a study of Ravanic *et al.* [9]. The recruited patients were adults in the majority of the included studies ranged from 24.5 ± 5.2 [10] to 47.6 ± 2.5 [11], while only three studies recruited children patients [8,12,13]. Two studies conducted among patients who treatment-naïve (first episode treatment) [10,14], while many of included studies were carried out in patients with treatment-resistant schizophrenia [8,11,13,15-19]. Several included studies flexible doses of clozapine as intervention which changes according to clinical requirement [8-10,13,15,20]. However, other studies used mean daily dose of 300 mg [11,12,19,21] or 500 mg [16,17]. The duration of clozapine treatment differed among included studies, many studies evaluated the efficacy after several weeks (few months) 3 -29 weeks [5,11,13,15-19,21,22], other studies had long follow-up periods (1-5 years) [9,10,14,20]. Moreover, two studies did initial assessment of clozapine efficacy after several weeks and then follow the patients for many years [8,12]. The medications used as a comparison to clozapine were olanzapine [5,8,13,16,18,19], risperidone [10,18,21,22], chlorpromazine [9,14,20], haloperidol [9,17,18,21], ziprasidone [15], and quetiapine [19], while two included studies had no comparison [11,12]. The most prevalent method used to assess the medication efficacy among included studies was PANSS [5,8-11,14-16,18,19,21], however mostly a combination of many assessment methods such as BPRS, CGI, SAPS, and SANS were used in many studies. Regarding the main outcome of the included studies, the efficacy of clozapine in treatment of schizophrenic patients, the results showed higher efficacy than any comparison medications in the majority of the studies [8-13,17-19,21,22]. Other studies found no significant differences [5,14,16,18,20] and a study conducted by Sacchetti *et al.* [15] reported lower efficacy of clozapine in comparison to ziprasidone.

DISCUSSION:

This review included studies evaluated the efficacy of clozapine on naïve-treatment and treatment resistant schizophrenic patients in the absence of other strategies such as pharmacological augmentation, adjunctive treatment, transcranial magnetic activation, or electrical convulsive treatment. The findings of this review showed that clozapine, even when used alone, had a significant efficacy on schizophrenic patients.

The findings showed that when the clozapine used in children or adolescents, it showed a superior efficacy than olanzapine [8,12,13]. Both medications were associated with side effects such as weight gain and metabolic abnormalities. Two studies used clozapine in treatment-naïve adult patients [10,14], one of them found slightly higher efficacy of clozapine than risperidone mainly attributed to the patient adherence [10], while other study found comparable efficacy of clozapine and chlorpromazine [14]. Thus, evidence of using clozapine in treatment-naïve patients was not robust. However, the efficacy of clozapine in treatment-resistant patients showed more consistent results with five studies out of seven studies reported better efficacy of clozapine than that of other antipsychotic medications [8,11,13,17,18]. All studies administered a small doses of clozapine (about 300 mg) found higher efficacy of clozapine [11,12,19,21]. This can be explained by low adverse effects that usually associated with small doses of clozapine which resulted in higher adherence rate and better outcomes of the treatment. Additionally, four studies followed the patients for long periods with two studies found comparable or lower efficacy of clozapine [14,20]. As the duration of treatment increased the discontinuation rate will be higher and that affected efficacy of clozapine. The interesting finding is the superior efficacy and the higher tolerability of ziprasidone than that of clozapine in a clinical trial of 147 treatment-refractory patients conducted by Sacchetti *et al.* [15]. This medication needs more investigations to support the evidence of its higher efficacy over clozapine in long follow up periods.

CONCLUSION:

This review supported the evidence of using clozapine in treatment-resistance patients either in adults or children schizophrenic patients, particularly when small doses were used. The ziprasidone is a promising drug which needs more studies to evaluate its efficacy and tolerability in the treatment of schizophrenic patients.

Table (1): The findings of the included studies regarding efficacy of the clozapine in comparison to other antipsychotic agents

Study	Sample size	Patient age mean (SD)	Population characteristics	Intervention Type and doses	Duration of treatment	Method of outcome assessment	Comparison (if any)	Conclusion
[10]	30 participants (15 in clozapine group and 15 in risperidone group)	Clozapine = 24.5 (5.2) Risperidone = 24.4 (5.3)	Patient first-episode treatment-naïve patients with schizophrenia or schizophreniform disorder (according to DSM-IV criteria) in the absence of other drugs or other psychiatric disorder	The dosage was prescribed according to the patient's situation as usual in clinical practice (started at 12.5 mg a day, maximum dosage of 900 for clozapine)	1 year	PANSS	The dosage was prescribed according to the patient's situation started at 2 mg, maximum dosage of 10 for risperidone	Clozapine may have a slightly superior efficacy in the initial year of treatment, and this can be explained for the most part by greater adherence to this treatment.
[11]	38 patients (5 patients discontinued and 33 completed the trial)	47.6 (2.5)	Patients were diagnosed according to DSM-IV criteria with treatment-resistant schizophrenia, and never had Global Assessment of Functioning (GAF) >41	The mean clozapine dose at 12 weeks was 328 mg/day (136 range: 75–600 mg/day)	3 weeks	PANSS	Not applicable	Significant improvements occurred in all PANSS scores by week 4, the first post-baseline psychopathology rating. Altogether, 50.0% of patients showed 20% reduction in PANSS total score, 20.6% had ≥30% reduction and 14.7% had >40% reduction

[21]	51 patients were randomly allocated into 3 groups (17 patients per group)	Clozapine group= 37.1 (9.4), haloperidol group= 33 (10.1), risperidone group= 32 (5.8)	Chronic schizophrenic patients with active phase of illness, and met DSM-IV-TR criteria	Clozapine (300 mg/day).	8 weeks	PANSS	Comparison to two groups: risperidone (6 mg/day) or haloperidol 15 mg/day	At week 8, a significant difference between clozapine group and each of risperidone and haloperidol
[14]	160 patients clozapine (n = 80) and chlorpromazine (n = 80)	28.7 (6.9)	Patients with treatment-naive, first episode schizophrenia or schizophreniform disorder according to Chinese version of the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV Axis I disorders	Clozapine	2 years	Chinese versions of the BPRS, PANSS, CGI, and GAF	Chlorpromazine	The results support the comparability in effectiveness between clozapine but with slightly greater tolerability of clozapine and chlorpromazine in the treatment of first-episode psychosis.

[15]	147 patients (73 in ziprasidone group and 74 in clozapine group) and 45 completed the trial in each group	Ziprasidone group= 41.6 (10.2) Clozapine group= 38 (11.2)	Patients with treatment-refractory schizophrenia. Patients had a DSM-IV diagnosis of schizophrenia, a history of resistance and/or intolerance to at least three acute cycles with different antipsychotics given at therapeutic doses	Clozapine was initiated at 25mg/day, titrated to 300 mg/day over 10 days and maintained at this dose for 1 week; thereafter, patients were flexibly dosed (250–600 mg/day)	18 weeks	PANSS	Ziprasidone was initiated at 80mg/day (dosed b.i.d.) for the first 3 days and flexibly dosed (80–160mg/day) thereafter	Ziprasidone but not clozapine showed a significant reduction of SAS and AIMS scores. Moreover, when compared with clozapine ziprasidone also had a more favorable metabolic profile,
[9]	325 patients randomized into groups of clozapine (n=115) haloperidol (105), chlorpromazine (n=105)	34.8	Patients with chronic schizophrenia established by DSM-IV criteria and excluding treatment naive schizophrenics.	clozapine (n=115, 75–600 mg)	5 years	GWB, PANSS, and CGI	Haloperidol (dose range 2–15 mg) Chlorpromazine (100–400 mg)	The statistically significant differences in all psychometric scores was found, for both schizophrenic syndromes, favoring clozapine

[12]	54 children and adolescents participated in double-blind (n = 22) or open-label (n = 32) clozapine trials	13.5 (2.5) at 6-week assessment	Children and adolescents who met DSM-III-R/DSM-IV criteria for schizophrenia with onset of psychosis before their 13th birthday were recruited	Clozapine dose, mg 298.2 (144.8) at 6 th weeks initial assessment and then 360.3 (96.9) for follow up period	Clinical evaluations took place at baseline, week 6 on clozapine, and at 2- to 6-year follow-up.	NDMC, CGI, CGAS, BPRS SAPS, and SANS	Not applicable	Clozapine is effective in treatment-resistant COS at 6 weeks. The long-term outcome of treatment-resistant children with COS seems to be best predicted by the improvement seen at 6 weeks and the majority of improvement occurring by week 6 of treatment.
[8]	25 patients Clozapine Group (n = 12) Olanzapine Group (n = 13)	Clozapine group=11.7 (2.3), olanzapine group=12.8 (2.4)	Children meeting unmodified DSM-IV criteria for schizophrenia, and resistant to treatment with at least 2 antipsychotics.	On the first night, children were given 5mg of clozapine. Further increases were guided by clinical judgment to a maximum 900 mg of clozapine	Double-blind randomized 8-week controlled trial, with a 2-year open-label follow-up.	CGI and PANSS	On the first night, children were given 5mg of the olanzapine dose was increased guided by clinical judgment to a maximum of 20 mg of	Clozapine was associated with a significant reduction in all outcome measures, whereas olanzapine showed a less consistent profile of clinical improvement. While there were moderate to large differential treatment effects in favor of clozapine, these reached significance only in the alleviation of negative symptoms from an antipsychotic-free baseline.
[13]	39 patients Clozapine n = 18 Olanzapine n = 21	Age range (10–18)	Children, ages 10–18 years, who met DSM-IV criteria for schizophrenia and who were resistant or intolerant to at least two antipsychotic drugs	Flexibly dosed treatment with clozapine	12 weeks of double-blind	BPRS and CGI	Olanzapine High-dose (up to 30 mg/day)	Clozapine was superior to olanzapine in terms of reduction of the psychosis cluster scores and negative symptoms from baseline to end point. However, both treatments were associated with significant weight-gain and related metabolic abnormalities.

[19]	99 clozapine (N=49), olanzapine [N=19], quetiapine [N=15], or risperidone [N=16])	39.7 (10.4)	Patients who discontinued treatment with ,olanzapine quetiapine, risperidone, or ziprasidone in phase 1 or 1B of the trials, primarily because of inadequate efficacy.	Modal dose of clozapine was 332.1 (156.9)	12 weeks	PANSS	Modal dose of olanzapine = 23.4 (7.9) and Quetiapine = 642.9 (195.0)	Clozapine was more effective than switching to another newer atypical .antipsychotic Safety monitoring is necessary to detect and manage clozapine's serious side effects.
[17]	71 patients Clozapine (n=37) and haloperidol (n=34)	Clozapine = 41 (10) , and haloperidol= 40 (8)	Patients met DSM-III-R18 diagnosis of schizophrenia or schizoaffective disorder with moderately refractory schizophrenia	Clozapine (target dosage, 500 mg/d)	29 weeks	BPRS, SANS, and CGI	Haloperidol (target dosage, 10 mg/d)	A higher proportion of clozapine-treated subjects met an a priori criterion of improvement compared with haloperidol. A greater improvement was seen in symptoms of psychosis, hostile-suspiciousness, anxiety-depression, thought disturbance, and total score measured on the Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale.
[18]	157 patients clozapine (N=40), olanzapine (N=39), risperidone ,(N=41) or haloperidol (N=37).	40.8 (9.2)	Patients were required to have a diagnosis of DSM-IV chronic schizophrenia or schizoaffective disorder and suboptimal response to previous treatment.	Clozapine	14 weeks (an 8-week escalation and fixed dose period followed by a 6-week -variable dose period).	PANSS	Olanzapine, risperidone, or haloperidol	Clozapine and olanzapine have similar general antipsychotic efficacy and that risperidone .may be somewhat less effective Clozapine was the most effective treatment ,for negative symptoms. However the differences among treatments were small.

[16]	177 patients olanzapine n = 75) or clozapine (n = 72)	37.6	Patients met the DSM-IV criteria for schizophrenia who failed to respond adequately to antipsychotic medication or who experienced intolerable adverse effects associated with the medication	clozapine (100–500 mg/day, n = 72)	18 weeks	PANSS and CGI-S	olanzapine (5–25 mg/day, n = 75)	Olanzapine demonstrated similar efficacy to clozapine in patients who had failed previous treatment because of lack of efficacy (treatment resistance) or intolerable side effects (treatment intolerance). Olanzapine therefore presents a safe alternative in the treatment of refractory schizophrenia
[20]	160 patients chlorpromazine (n=81) Clozapine (n=83)	28.7(6.9)	Patients met the DSM-IV criteria for schizophrenia	Clozapine dosages were increased using a standardized regimen during the first 28 days of admission (to a maximum of 400 mg/day)	1 year	Chinese version of the BPRS, the Chinese version of (SANS), (CGI), (GAF), and (SAESS)	Chlorpromazine doses were increased using a standardized regimen during the first 28 days of admission (to a maximum of 600 mg/day of)	No difference in the proportion of first-episode patients receiving clozapine or chlorpromazine that achieved remission. However, first episode patients receiving chlorpromazine remitted significantly faster and remained in remission longer than subjects receiving clozapine. While the chlorpromazine group showed significantly less symptomatology on some measures and fewer side effects at 12 weeks.

[22]	273 patients Clozapine (n= 126) or Risperidone (n=130)	Clozapin e group= 37.8 (10.4) Risperid one group= 39.5 (11.3)	Patients with severe chronic schizophrenia who met the DSM-IV criteria for schizophrenia	Clozapine group	12 weeks	BPRS and CGI	Risperidone	Clozapine showed superior efficacy over risperidone in this patient population. Both treatments were equally well tolerated as demonstrated through their adverse event profiles, although as expected clozapine was associated with a lower risk of extrapyramidal symptoms than risperidone.
[5]	180 patients (olanzapine: n = 90 and clozapine: n = 90)	38.6 (10.6)	Patients who met with a clinical diagnosis of DSM-IV criteria for schizophrenia	Clozapine	18 weeks	PANSS, CGI-S, and BPRS	Olanzapine	There were no statistically significant differences between treatment groups on baseline efficacy measures, and although the PANSS Total scores were numerically different, they were not statistically significantly different. Both treatment groups showed significant within-group improvement from baseline to end point.

PANSS = Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale, NDMC = N-desmethylclozapine; CGI = Clinical Global Impressions; CGAS = Children_s Global Assessment Scale; BPRS = Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale; SAPS = Scale for the Assessment of Positive Symptoms; SANS = Scale for the Assessment of Negative Symptoms.

REFERENCES:

1. Austin J. Schizophrenia: an update and review. *Journal of genetic counseling* 2005;14(5):329-40.
2. Aleman A, Kahn RS, Selten J-P. Sex differences in the risk of schizophrenia: evidence from meta-analysis. *Archives of general psychiatry* 2003;60(6):565-71.
3. McGorry PD, Yung AR. Early intervention in psychosis: an overdue reform. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry* 2003;37(4):393-8.
4. Lieberman JA, Stroup TS, McEvoy JP, Swartz MS, Rosenheck RA, Perkins DO et al. Effectiveness of antipsychotic drugs in patients with chronic schizophrenia. *New England Journal of Medicine* 2005;353(12):1209-23.
5. Tollefson GD, Birkett MA, Kiesler GM, Wood AJ, Group LRSS. Double-blind comparison of olanzapine versus clozapine in schizophrenic patients clinically eligible for treatment with clozapine. *Biological psychiatry* 2001;49(1):52-63.
6. Slotema CW, Dirk Blom J, Hoek HW, Sommer IE. Should we expand the toolbox of psychiatric treatment methods to include Repetitive Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (rTMS)? A meta-analysis of the efficacy of rTMS in psychiatric disorders. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry* 2010;71(7):873.
7. Havaki-Kontaxaki BJ, Ferentinos PP, Kontaxakis VP, Paplos KG, Soldatos CR. Concurrent administration of clozapine and electroconvulsive therapy in clozapine-resistant schizophrenia. *Clinical neuropharmacology* 2006;29(1):52-6.
8. Shaw P, Sporn A, Gogtay N, Overman GP, Greenstein D, Gochman P et al. Childhood-onset schizophrenia: a double-blind, randomized clozapine-olanzapine comparison. *Archives of general psychiatry* 2006;63(7):721-30.
9. Ravanic DB, Dejanovic SMD, Janjic V, Jovic SD, Milovanovic DR, Jakovljevic V et al. Effectiveness of clozapine, haloperidol and chlorpromazine in schizophrenia during a five-year period. *Arquivos de neuro-psiquiatria* 2009;67(2A):195-202.
10. Fuentenebro J, Taboada D, Palomo T, Aragües M, Ovejero S, Del Alamo C et al. Randomized trial of clozapine vs. risperidone in treatment-naïve first-episode schizophrenia: results after one year. *Schizophrenia research* 2013;149(1-3):156-61.
11. Kishi T, Fujita K, Furukawa O, Suzuki T, Moriwaki M, Nitta M et al. Efficacy and tolerability of clozapine in Japanese patients with treatment-resistant schizophrenia: results from a 12-week, flexible dose study using raters masked to antipsychotic choice. *Asian journal of psychiatry* 2013;6(3):200-7.
12. Sporn AL, Vermani A, Greenstein DK, Bobb AJ, Spencer EP, Clasen LS et al. Clozapine treatment of childhood-onset schizophrenia: evaluation of effectiveness, adverse effects, and long-term outcome. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry* 2007;46(10):1349-56.
13. Kumra S, Kranzler H, Gerbino-Rosen G, Kester HM, DeThomas C, Kafantaris V et al. Clozapine and "high-dose" olanzapine in refractory early-onset schizophrenia: a 12-week randomized and double-blind comparison. *Biological psychiatry* 2008;63(5):524-9.
14. Girgis RR, Phillips MR, Li X, Li K, Jiang H, Wu C et al. Clozapine v. chlorpromazine in treatment-naïve, first-episode schizophrenia: 9-year outcomes of a randomised clinical trial. *The British Journal of Psychiatry* 2011;199(4):281-8.
15. Sacchetti E, Galluzzo A, Valsecchi P, Romeo F, Gorini B, Warrington L et al. Ziprasidone vs clozapine in schizophrenia patients refractory to multiple antipsychotic treatments: the MOZART study. *Schizophrenia research* 2009;113(1):112-21.
16. Bitter I, Dossenbach MR, Brook S, Feldman PD, Metcalfe S, Gagiano CA et al. Olanzapine versus clozapine in treatment-resistant or treatment-intolerant schizophrenia. *Progress in Neuro-Psychopharmacology and Biological Psychiatry* 2004;28(1):173-80.
17. Kane JM, Marder SR, Schooler NR, Wirshing WC, Umbricht D, Baker RW et al. Clozapine and haloperidol in moderately refractory schizophrenia: a 6-month randomized and double-blind comparison. *Archives of general psychiatry* 2001;58(10):965-72.
18. Volavka J, Czobor P, Sheitman B, Lindenmayer J-P, Citrome L, McEvoy JP et al. Clozapine, olanzapine, risperidone, and haloperidol in the treatment of patients with chronic schizophrenia and schizoaffective disorder. *Focus* 2004;159(1):255-67.
19. McEvoy JP, Lieberman JA, Stroup TS, Davis SM, Meltzer HY, Rosenheck RA et al. Effectiveness of clozapine versus olanzapine, quetiapine, and risperidone in patients with chronic schizophrenia who did not respond to prior atypical antipsychotic treatment. *American*

Journal of Psychiatry 2006;163(4):600-10.
20.

Lieberman JA, Phillips M, Gu H, Stroup S, Zhang P, Kong L et al. Atypical and conventional antipsychotic drugs in treatment-naive first-episode schizophrenia: a 52-week randomized trial of clozapine vs chlorpromazine.

Neuropsychopharmacology 2003;28(5):995.
21.

Ghaleiha A, Honarbakhsh N, Boroumand MA, Jafarinia M, Tabrizi M, Rezaei F et al. Correlation of adenosinergic activity with superior efficacy of clozapine for treatment of chronic schizophrenia: a double blind randomised trial. Human Psychopharmacology: Clinical and Experimental 2011;26(2):120-4.

Azorin22.

J-M, Spiegel R, Remington G, Vanelle J-M, Péré J-J, Giguere M et al. A double-blind comparative study of clozapine and risperidone in the management of severe chronic schizophrenia. American Journal of Psychiatry 2001;158(8):1305-13.